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RESISTIRÉ

Reducing gendered inequalities
caused by COVID-19 policies

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List of acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
FS	Factsheet
GIA	Gender impact assessment
GBV	Gender-based violence
NR	National Researcher
NRRP	National Recovery and Resilience Plan
WP	Work Package

Table of Content

Introduction	5
Background.....	5
Outline of the project	6
The mapping process in WP 2	7
The WP2 contribution to the overall project	10
Results.....	12
Cycle 1 – Understanding the initial responses	12
Cycle 2 – Recovery and Resilience	19
Cycle 3 – Learning from civil society	27
Conclusions.....	33
Recommendations	34
Further research	36
References	38
Acknowledgements	43

Introduction

This document represents the overall report of Work Package (WP) 2 of the RESISTIRE project, in which the results of the analyses carried out during the 3 cycles are summarised, together with some general reflections on the evolution of policy and societal responses to the COVID-19 pandemic crisis. For more detailed information, please refer to the 3 reports developed during the 3 project phases (Cibin et al. 2021; Cibin et al. 2022; Cibin et al. 2023).

Background

The COVID-19 pandemic resulted in the introduction of national policies and actions to control the spread of the virus and reduce deaths. This led to significant changes in people's lives, with physical and social distancing becoming the norm. Measures such as quarantine and self-isolation were commonly implemented. As a result, there was a rise in remote work, home-schooling, and increased reliance on online platforms.

The pandemic has also led to layoffs, job cuts, financial difficulties, mental health challenges, disruptions in regular medical care, and sadly, the death of many people (Nicola et al. 2020; Van Bavel 2020; Lewnard & Lo 2020). These outcomes have disproportionately impacted marginalised communities, intensifying pre-existing vulnerabilities and inequalities. For instance, initial reports indicated an increase in domestic violence, limited accessibility to personal assistance for people with disabilities, targeting of minorities through hate speech, heightened xenophobia and racism towards individuals of Asian descent, reinforcement of bioessentialism, and wrongful dismissal of individuals with caregiving responsibilities (John et al. 2020; Sikka 2020).

Additionally, individuals working in healthcare, education, and service sectors, where direct interaction with other people is necessary, have faced heightened risks (OECD 2022). To tackle labour shortages, certain European Union administrations have implemented mutual agreements to ease travel limitations, enabling specific professionals like nurses and agricultural workers to migrate. Nevertheless, this has disproportionately endangered individuals from economically marginalised nations (Rogozanu & Gabor 2020).

These dynamics, like those of other crises, are influenced by inequalities such as gender, sex, age, disability, ethnicity/race, migration status, religion, and social class. These inequality grounds intersect with one another and have been discussed in various sources (Lokot & Avakyan 2020; Walter & McGregor 2020; Walby 2015; Walby et al. 2012). The consequences of these impacts are not uniform and exhibit disparities among different groups, with uncertain long-term effects (Cumming et al. 2020). From

the beginning, evidence indicated that the consequences of COVID-19 have disproportionately affected women, who were more susceptible due to their roles as frontline workers and caregivers, both formally and informally (Denis 2022). For this reason, it has been essential to consider gender aspects in relation to social class, ethnicity, age, and other inequality grounds, and analyse how policy responses to the pandemic have adopted, or not, a "gender+" perspective, recognising both the advantages and disadvantages experienced by different groups. To do this, the RESISTIRÉ project was designed to analyse how various policy responses contributed to unequal outcomes and exacerbate existing inequalities, as well as how alternative responses could have been implemented to address gender and intersectional inequalities across different policy domains (Lombardo & Kantola 2019).

Outline of the project

The objective of RESISTIRÉ has been to understand and offer insights and solutions to address the unequal impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic and the policy and societal responses across 30 countries, including the EU-27 (minus Malta), Iceland, Serbia, Turkey, and the UK. It has aimed to enhance individual and societal resilience.

RESISTIRÉ builds on an intersectional and gender+ theoretical approach (Verloo 2013). The project focuses on the intersection of specific domains of gender inequalities (work and the labour market, the economy, the gender pay and pension gaps, the gender care gap, gender-based violence (GBV), decision-making and politics, human and fundamental rights, and environmental justice) with selected inequality grounds (sex and/or gender, sexual orientation, ethnicity, nationality, class, age, religion/belief, disability, and gender identity).

The overall methodology is based on a step-by-step process implemented in three cycles over 30 months (April 2021 - September 2023). All project activities are organised in the three cycles, feeding results into one another, including feedback loops between the cycles. The project involves an eleven-partner multidisciplinary and multisectoral European consortium and a well-established network of researchers in the 30 countries. RESISTIRÉ has engaged in policy analysis, quantitative analysis, and qualitative research to inform the development of innovative solutions. By adopting co-created and inclusive strategies, RESISTIRÉ has sought to tackle both existing and emerging patterns of inequality in line with the domains outlined by the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (United Nations 2015) and in the European Commission Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 (EC 2019).

The mapping process in WP 2

This report represents the final deliverable of the activities of WP 2, which focused on mapping pandemic-related policies and civil society responses to mitigate the unequal impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, as stated in the Grant Agreement, the goal of this WP has been:

- Mapping of COVID-19 policies as a reference point to analyse the behaviour as well as impacts at economic, social, and environmental levels. This covers the general COVID-19 policies, but also policies developed towards specific target groups, whether to remediate or reduce (negative) impacts, or not.
- Collect examples of actions developed by different stakeholders (NGOs, civil society, local governments, etc.) to alleviate or remediate the impact on specific target groups.
- Share examples of promising practices to inspire policymakers and stakeholders.

Theoretical framework

The research process within this WP has been built on Feminist (New) Institutionalism (Mackay et al. 2010), an approach that observes institutions as a fundamental variable to be considered in political analysis and offers a solution to the dualism between structure and agency by considering both elements as co-constituent of political dynamics and societal change. Change is conceptualised in terms of 'bounded agency' (Mackay et al. 2010, p. 583), in which '[s]trategic actors initiate change within a context of opportunities and constraints' (Ibid. p. 583) and where relations and institutions are gendered. Feminist (New) Institutionalism underlines how political relations together with formal and informal institutions are all gendered and need to be observed through a feminist lens. For this reason, the analysis within RESISTIRÉ is based on an intersectional approach called gender+, which focuses on the observation of gender inequalities without losing sight of their interaction with other factors of inequality.

Methods

In the three cycles of this project the data for the analysis were generated by 30 national researchers (NRs), representing the EU-27 countries (minus Malta), along with Iceland, Serbia, Turkey, and the UK. Nine of the NRs have been part of the project's partner teams, while the other 21 were identified through a network of professional connections among members of the consortium. Most of them are researchers and experts in gender studies and inequality studies.

During the three cycles, the data gathering process was based on the preparation of data collection grids and the completion of these by the NRs. The grids consisted of both closed-ended and open-ended questions. In the first and second cycles, this task was conducted mainly through desk research, whereas in the third cycle, desk research was supplemented by semi-structured interviews with experts. During the first cycle, the NRs

also produced a report on the situation of gender+ inequalities in the country of reference. Table 1 summarises the data collected and analysed in the three cycles.

Table 1 Summary of the data collected and analysed in the 3 cycles of the project

	Period	Policies mapped	CSO's initiatives mapped	Interviews with CSO's representatives	No. Of countries	Reference
<i>CYCLE I</i>	15 May - 30 Jun 2021	298 (+ 29 country reports)	277		29	Cibin et al. 2021
<i>CYCLE II</i>	1 Dec 2021 - 30 Jan 2022	31 (National Recovery and Resilience Plans)			30	Cibin et al. 2022
<i>CYCLE III</i>	12 Sep - 14 Oct 2022		49 (+ 79 already mapped in cycle 1)	31	30	Cibin et al. 2023
Total		329	326	31		

All the data were analysed by means of thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke 2006) using a combination of top-down (predefined codebooks) and bottom-up (e.g., open codes) approaches. When possible, we analysed the closed questions from the grids by creating frequency tables and graphs to provide the most relevant contextual data on the mapped policies and initiatives. In addition to the data produced for this WP, the NRs worked to the collection of quantitative data for WP 3 and of interviews with experts and narratives with people in precarious and vulnerable groups for WP 4 (Figure 1). These activities have been repeated in three cycles over the course of the project's duration.

Figure 1 RESISTIRÉ methodological step-by-step three-cycle process

Topics and Material

During the first cycle, the aim of the mapping was to describe and analyse the gender dimensions and impacts of policies and societal responses implemented in Europe in the course of and in relation to the COVID-19 pandemic. To this end, between 15 May and 30 June 2021, the NRs identified the relevant response, analysed them, and produced 298 policy grids, 277 societal initiatives grids, and 29 country reports.

The analysis in the first cycle revealed a lack of policy attention to gender issues and to the inequalities experienced by many vulnerable groups during the initial phases of the pandemic. The increasing difficulties experienced by these groups were also confirmed by the analyses within WP 3 and 4. Discussions with working groups and with experts and stakeholders took place throughout the first cycle on how these problems should be addressed at different levels. These discussions combined with the consortium's observations led to the decision to focus the second cycle of the project's analysis on the recovery policy solutions suggested and implemented. Therefore, it was decided that WP 2 would focus its analysis on the National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRP) (or equivalent recovery policies for those countries not in the EU but targeted by the RESISTIRÉ project). These plans are in fact the most important instrument the EU has put in place to provide economic support to member states for the socio-economic recovery from the pandemic. The analysis was aimed at understanding whether and how those policies considered domains of gender inequalities and inequality grounds. We observed that, in general, these policies aimed at recovering from the pandemic's health, economic, and social effects lacked gender mainstreaming and intersectional approaches (Cibin et al. 2022), and that the lack of involvement of civil society in the design of these plans often contributed to this result.

The analyses conducted in the quantitative (WP3) and qualitative (WP4) work packages in the project's second cycle helped to highlight how the process of socio-economic recovery from the consequences of the pandemic was not yet underway for women and vulnerable groups. On the one hand, the quantitative data emphasised even more strongly how COVID-19 policies had contributed to exacerbating existing inequalities and how more specific data needed to be produced to better understand the severity of the situation (Stovell et al. 2022). On the other hand, the analysis of stories and experiences collected from vulnerable people, stakeholders and experts, highlighted how the lack of a recovery process was evident in people's lives since one of the main findings was that "the most vulnerable are even more vulnerable, the most marginalised are even more marginalised" (Sandström et al. 2022). The reflection around these findings within the project teams' discussion and co-creation exercises prompted the definition of the objective of the third cycle on better understanding what practices and kinds of actions can contribute to reversing the developments that deepen inequality. The goal was to learn from the strategies and promising practices that civil society organisations (CSOs) and vulnerable individuals have put in place to cope with the

consequences of the pandemic and discover how public policies can support them in these efforts. The concept of 'better stories' proposed by Dina Georgis (2013) has been used to identify actions that have been possible within civil society to trigger change in situations of inequalities and vulnerabilities and that could be inspiring for public authorities as well as other CSOs. To this end, the NRs identified 31 of these stories and interviewed representatives of the CSOs that made them possible.

The WP2 contribution to the overall project

The mapping processes within WP2 was also useful to continue offering an overview of the institutional framework and interactions at the macro- and meso-levels within the different topics considered in the three cycles. This was part of a composite dialogue with the other working groups, which were more focused on providing quantitative contextual data within WP3 (mainly macro-level) and the analysis of dynamics at the micro level within WP4.

The key findings of the WP2 contributed to the co-creative processes within the Open Studios (WP5), that are workshops where different experts and stakeholders were involved to co-create innovative solutions. WP2 contributed both by directly influencing the main theme of some of these workshops and by providing data and findings aimed at building tools to promote dialogue between participants, such as personas, better stories etc. (Kerremans, Živković & Denis 2021; Kerremans & Denis 2022; 2023).

The findings made within the research process described in this report strongly influenced the topic of some of the factsheets (FS containing operational recommendations developed within WP63, and in particular:

- FS 1 - Pandemic and Gender Mainstreaming;
- FS 2 - Women's Representation, Diversity and Inclusion in Decision-Making;
- FS 12 - The Missing Perspectives of Women in the National Recovery and Resilience Plans;
- FS13 - Striving for Social Justice.

In general, the data and findings produced within WP2 have been used in the design of all the FS developed by the project. They have contributed to the bases for the discussions within the Open Studios that brought the definition of the other FSs and the pilot projects, implemented by and with CSOs (Ghidoni et al. 2023). The research gaps identified during the phases of desk research and data analysis have been used for the

³ All the project's FS containing operational recommendations are available at the following link <https://resistire-project.eu/recommendations/>

construction of the project's research agendas⁴.

The better stories identified along the three cycles have been published on the project website⁵ and represent an interesting database of good practices to deal with inequalities during crisis situations. The contacts collected during the mapping processes have been fundamental for the advocacy process of the project within WP7.

⁴ The research agendas developed by the project can be found at the following link <https://resistire-project.eu/research-agendas/>

⁵ <https://resistire-project.eu/better-stories-europe/>

Results

Cycle 1 – Understanding the initial responses

Aims

The purpose of the mapping of policy and societal responses in the first cycle was to gather as much information as possible to try to obtain a comprehensive understanding of how gender+ inequalities were managed (or not) in the early stages of the pandemic. The analysis of the existing literature on the consequences of such crisis situations and the initial effects of the pandemic already offered some indications of how women and vulnerable groups were at greater risk of encountering both health and socio-economic problems (e.g., Walter & McGregor 2020; Donà 2021). At the same time, there were already some indications of how these specific categories were not in the radar of those policies designed to respond to the crisis (Wenham et al. 2020).

For this reason, initially, all the eight specific domains of gender inequalities and all the specific vulnerability grounds under the lens of RESISTIRÉ have been considered in the mapping. Based on the initial analysis and conceptual and policy considerations, we later decided to focus the report on four main domains: GBV; work and the labour market; the gender care gap; and human and fundamental rights. The NRs were asked to explain the policy measures taken at national and regional level in relation to all these specific domains and inequality grounds. Simultaneously, they were required to underline any actions that were not taken, aspects that were overlooked or absent from the policies, efforts made by societal actors to compensate for the lack of public intervention, and the specific actors involved in the process, as well as those who were excluded. The policies have been analysed from the point of view of their design, implementation, monitoring, evaluation, and the omissions from a gender+ perspective. A total of 298 grids have been filled out by the NR with such information about policies.

CSOs' initiatives aimed at mitigating the inequalities have been mapped using the following criteria: innovative and promising action; proposing initiatives representative of different domains and countries; initiatives supporting different types of vulnerability; initiatives that are transferable and reproduced in other contexts. 277 grids have been filled out by the NR with such information about civil society's initiatives.

Finally, NRs provided 29 country reports containing description of national and subnational COVID-19 policies, and the responses from civil society, from a gender+ point of view. For a more comprehensive and detailed analysis, please consult Cibir and colleagues (2021).

Key findings

Domains and inequality grounds addressed

The 298 policies mapped by the NRs were mostly dealing with topics related to work and labour market (one in two policies) and human rights (43%) (see Figure 2). The other two domains most present, albeit to a more marginal extent, are those of the economy and the gender care gap, each involving 26% of the policies. Slightly more than one in ten policies deal with GBV or the pay/pension gap and there is almost no interest in issues relating to environmental justice and decision-making.

Figure 2 Percentage of grids identified in the individual policy domains (N= 298)

The most frequent grounds are age and class (see Figure 3), which are present in more than eighty policies out of the total (28% and 27%, respectively). This is followed by disability (24%), nationality (14%), gender identity (10%), and ethnicity (10%). The analysis of the interaction between these grounds shows that 13% of the policies concern class and age, 10% class and disability, and 12% age and disability.

Figure 3 Percentage of policies identified that address specific inequality grounds (N= 298)

At the same time, we observed that of the 277 civil society initiatives mapped, the issue of human rights was the preponderant one (more than two out of three initiatives considered), followed, to a much lesser extent, by GBV (29%), work and labour market (28%) and gender care gap (24%).

Concerning the inequality grounds, we observed that the most frequent ground is class, which is present in about half of the mapped initiatives (47%). This is followed by ethnicity (36%), age (35%), and nationality (32%).

In general, we observed that the initial policies implemented to address the socioeconomic consequences of the pandemic did not adequately address issues concerning gender inequalities and other intersecting vulnerabilities, such as gender identity, nationality, and age. This deficiency was particularly evident during the initial phase of the crisis, as described in the following sections.

Gender-based violence

The discussions and measures concerning GBV are those where we observed the most focused attention on gender related issues. This domain concerns only one in three of the mapped policies despite many countries have experienced an increase in GBV due to lockdown policies and the economic crisis. In response, several countries have implemented policies aimed at raising awareness, strengthening remote support tools, and allocating funds to organisations that provide services and shelters, often in collaboration with CSOs. However, it is important to note that some countries lack policies addressing this issue, while in other cases, policymakers have only issued statements without taking tangible actions.

Work and Labour market

During the pandemic, another significant aspect that required attention was addressing work and income accessibility. To prevent the spread of the infection, various limitations were imposed, or economic activities were halted by public authorities. This situation posed challenges for numerous individuals, with a particularly pronounced impact on those already vulnerable. To address the repercussions of workplace closures, stay-at-home orders, and increased unemployment, several countries gradually implemented measures such as: providing income support and compensation, initiating job retention programs, adopting more flexible work arrangements, promoting remote work, and expanding unemployment benefits. However, these measures often focused on specific sectors and certain segments of the population, leaving particular groups of individuals, especially women, in a challenging position. For example, few resources have been invested in helping the staff of health and care facilities, who are predominantly women. Almost no support was given to atypical or informal workers and the so-called 'non-regulars'.

Gender care gap

The analysis underlined how issues related to the domain of gender care gap are closely intertwined with the one related to work. In particular, we stressed how the impact of measures aimed at containing the virus and the subsequent reorganisation of work and the labour market has had significant implications for care activities and unpaid work. Most countries have had to close kindergartens, schools, and other related services and the consequence has been a growing concern related to the management of children and their education. To face this situation, public authorities have implemented various strategies, including the extension of parental leave, care allowances, and reduced working hours. The majority of these actions have failed to address the intersecting inequalities adequately. Just a few of measures showed awareness of the need to offer specific support to particular vulnerable groups, such as single mothers and individuals with disabilities, as for instance in Poland where financial support was offered to people with disabilities for provision of care at home. Consequently, these measures have reinforced gender divisions in labour and placed a heavier burden of unpaid care work on women. Furthermore, in most of the considered cases, the eligibility criteria for accessing incentives and benefits have often disadvantaged specific groups, such as the self-employed, individuals with non-standard employment contracts, and informal workers, many of whom are migrant workers. It is noteworthy that these measures have often been heteronormative in nature, primarily targeting fathers and mothers.

Human and fundamental rights

The pandemic restrictions and lockdown policies had significant implications for safeguarding human and fundamental rights. On one side, we observed how many public authorities implemented measures to enhance digital education accessibility for students, provide shelter for vulnerable groups like the homeless, and ease restrictions

on healthcare access. On the other side, these measures were mostly short-term exceptions and failed to address structural inequalities. Some governments temporarily loosened their typically strict immigration policies just for the concern that a shortage of immigrant labour might have hindered citizens' access to essential goods and care. The impact of pandemic policies on human rights was evident across different groups. In certain nations, asylum seekers and migrants, particularly those in camps, faced discrimination and barriers to essential services. Many women were deprived of fundamental birthing rights, including the right to have their partners present. The Hungarian government took advantage of the crisis to enact a constitutional amendment during the state of emergency, effectively curbing the rights of LGBTQI+ communities.

The response from civil society

Initiatives introduced by CSOs have served as both supplements and counteractions to COVID-related policies aimed at addressing inequalities. Numerous approaches have been taken by these groups to combat these disparities. Some have focused on gathering and analysing data to bring attention to the existing inequities, while others have dedicated their efforts to raising awareness and organising protest campaigns, advocating for the rights of vulnerable groups. These initiatives have taken various forms, ranging from practical assistance such as distributing essential goods and providing shelter, to establishing mutual aid platforms that facilitate the exchange of goods and services. Additionally, informational materials have been created and disseminated to reach individuals in need who may not have access to official channels of information. Furthermore, CSOs have also extended health and psychological support to those requiring assistance.

Obstacles

In situations where public institutions have deployed some tools to try to mitigate the negative effects of the pandemic, we have recorded many cases where people belonging to vulnerable groups have been faced with three types of obstacles that have contributed to limiting their access:

- issues related to dynamics of digital exclusion (e.g., the possibility of accessing certain services only through online platforms), in a historical situation where the digital transition of services and private interactions has accelerated without reflecting on alternatives for those without the access to technology or know-how;
- language barriers that in some cases excluded specific groups of people from communicative processes in a situation of uncertainty where finding information was essential (e.g., the lack of translation of some public communications);
- complicated procedures and heavy bureaucracy attached to the process of applying for certain services which once again penalises the less educated, those with lower cognitive abilities or language barriers.

The policies design processes

Our preliminary analysis indicated that in numerous countries, at national and regional level, men predominantly occupied the key decision-making roles concerning the pandemic response. Some exceptions were found in some governments (e.g., Austria, Belgium, Finland, Lithuania) and expert committees (e.g., Turkey, Iceland, Slovenia) where the gender balance was more present. We collected mixed feedback from the NR about the existence of a potential correlation between the gender composition of decision-makers and the gender sensitivity of policies: more research on this topic is needed.

In addition, in the analysis of the policies design processes, we observed a notable absence of interaction between policymakers and experts in the field of inequalities, as well as representatives from civil society and marginalised communities. The main justification for this problem that was observed was that the urgency of addressing the crisis hindered governments from seeking input from experts and diverse groups. Frequently, it was only during the later stages of the pandemic, often due to pressure from protest movements, that governments started to pay attention to the perspectives of these individuals.

Conclusions

The examination of the initial policy response to the pandemic revealed that policymakers placed significant emphasis on striking a balance between safeguarding public health and preserving economic productivity, particularly in the initial phase. However, even though gender mainstreaming has been the accepted approach in EU policymaking for more than twenty years, our analysis underlined how the policies to respond to the pandemic crisis were not extensively mainstreamed at the national level.

Several instances highlighted by the NR indicated that these policies were rooted in an implicit idea of society as cisgender, made of "conventional" and "typical" families (consisting of individuals with citizenship and standard employment contracts), with two parents and one or two children. Within this framework, women were predominantly viewed as responsible for unpaid caregiving activities, as well as holding essential positions such as healthcare workers, domestic workers, cashiers, and so on. We observed that the pandemic created more attention on the topic of care work and how heavy and overburdening it can be. However, the pandemic and its associated measures seem to have failed to emphasise the disproportionate burden of care placed on women. Unfortunately, many policies aimed at reorganising work and providing assistance for family and household responsibilities have simply perpetuated traditional gender roles. Our suggestion to policymakers is to integrate efforts to address the gender care gap with initiatives to reduce inequalities in the workplace, while addressing the issue of care as a logic of organising, in opposition to choice (Mol 2008),

and as part of ongoing theoretical preoccupations with matters of care (de la Bellacasa 2017).

In the area of GBV, we observed how collaboration between central institutions and regional/local organisations have been strategically significant, especially with organisations directly assisting victims. We recognise the extreme importance of those policies focused to support victims, however, the efforts to address GBV should extend beyond providing psychological and housing support to victims and should encompass a broader perspective. This perspective should include considerations of tackling issues such as female unemployment, immigrant regularisation, and discrimination against LGBTQI* communities. Furthermore, it is crucial to note that the policies implemented, with a few exceptions, seldom adopt an intersectional approach in their proposed measures and frequently fail to include marginalised groups of individuals. In addition, the almost complete lack of attention to measures aimed at preventing the actions of predominantly male perpetrators need to be addressed. Moreover, we noticed a tendency on relying solely on the goodwill and grassroots initiatives of CSOs for data collection and processing on GBV. This is evident in the words of the representative of a Slovak CSOs supporting Roma women:

'We had families where their members spent some time separately, the children were at school, the wife at home, but the man was at work and suddenly they were all together inside a house. It created various stress situations. In one community we saw a rise in domestic violence, but also drinking increased among some women. These are things we are not able to solve professionally, but we know about them as we do the mapping of communities and we are trying to find ways for individual aid, but we do not have the tools to solve this on a community level, we were just mapping what was going on in communities...'

For this reason, there is a pressing need for systematic generation and widespread dissemination of detailed data at the institutional level, such as national and regional public authorities.

Cycle 2 – Recovery and Resilience

Aims

After analysing, in the first cycle, those policies that represented an immediate response to the pandemic, in the second cycle the focus shifted to those measures and actions designed to support the process of 'reconstruction' of the socio-economic organisation in the various countries. During the different sessions of discussion and co-construction of ideas with experts and stakeholders within the first project cycle, it emerged that NRRP6 were very important tools on which most EU member states would base their post-pandemic crisis response policies. Gender equality has been set as a cross-cutting priority for the plans and this represented an opportunity to compare how different countries translated (or not) gender-related issues into their policy agenda. For this reason, the need to analyse how these plans took gender+ inequality issues into account quickly became evident. For those non-EU countries involved in the project, we decided to identify and analyse one (or more, if available and time permitting) equivalent national policy aimed at socioeconomic recovery from the pandemic. From the 1st of December 2021 to the 31st of January 2022 the NR filled out 26 grids with information related to their related NRRPs and five grids focusing non-EU national policies aimed at socioeconomic recovery.

The analysis was aimed at understanding, first of all, whether and how NRRPs and equivalent policies considered the domains of gender inequalities and inequality grounds at the centre of the RESISTIRÉ approach, or other inequalities that emerged or deepened specifically during the pandemic. In addition, our investigation delved into the extent and manner in which stakeholders and civil society actors have actively participated in shaping the policies, as well as their primary responses to the document's contents and the overall design procedure.

Information gathered through desk-research and literature analysis revealed that EC required that 37% of the planned expenses should contribute positively to the climate transition and that a minimum of 20% of the expenditures should be allocated to the digital transition. Gender equality was set as a cross-cutting priority for the plans. However, this issue was not included among the 11 main criteria used by the Commission to assess the plans (Sapala 2021) and no specific budget was allocated for

⁶ In response to the social and economic challenges arising from the pandemic, European Union (EU) Member States came together in 2021 and established the Next Generation EU (NGEU). The primary mechanism for distributing the majority of NGEU funds (€723.8 billion) to Member States is the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF). To access these funds, Member States are required to develop a NRRP that outlines a set of reforms and investments that individual states must undertake by 2026. For more information, see Cibin and colleagues (2022).

related measures.

Previous analysis of some plans warned about the lack of adequate representation of the women's perspectives, the challenges related to the implementation of gender equality objectives, and how funding green and digital transitions without clear guidelines could lead to a predominantly male workforce (Sapala 2021). Zarra and Ceron (2021) underlined how the concept of gender equality remains a secondary focus in the plans, and its presence is largely hidden amidst the reforms and investments outlined in the documents. However, their analysis showed the presence of indications of slightly heightened awareness regarding these matters in the plans of countries that have previously demonstrated sensitivity towards those topics. Spain and Sweden have emerged as exemplary nations in this regard. For a more comprehensive and detailed analysis, please consult Cibin and colleagues (2022).

Key findings

Domains and inequality grounds addressed

The general feedback from most of the NR involved in the analysis of the NRRPs was that the documents approached gender issues and vulnerable groups only in a vague and general way or only as a side effect of measures with other objectives. In any case, Figure 4 offers a picture of how this is translated in the different domains considered by the project, showing how many plans mention each specific domain. The main focus revolves around the domain of work and the labour market, which is referred to in 81% of the documents (21 plans). This is closely followed by education (77%, 20 plans) and the gender care gap (73%, 19 plans). On the other side, a mere 31% of the plans (8 plans in total) acknowledged the issue of GBV, despite the surge in cases observed during the pandemic. Similarly, both the domain of environmental justice and the one of decision-making and politics were addressed in a relatively small proportion, respectively 46% (12 plans) and 42% (11 plans).

Figure 4 Percentage of plans that mention each domain (N=26). (Question: Does the plan include projects/actions/measures aimed at mitigating sex/gender inequalities in the following domains? Please, highlight explicit mentions of intersecting inequality grounds, if any)

In terms of inequality grounds, almost all plans (25 plans, only Latvia is missing) mentioned elements or measures aimed at addressing age-based inequalities (see Figure 5). Similarly, a very significant portion (92%, 24 plans except Sweden and Finland) considers social class and socioeconomic background disparities. Approximately 81% of the plans mention inequalities pertaining to disability. At the same time, there is a notable lack of attention given to matters concerning religion and belief, gender identity, and sexual orientation. About half of the plans (42%, 11 plans) incorporate content mentioning inequalities related to nationality, or ethnicity (50%, 13 plans).

Figure 5 % of plans mentioning each inequality ground

It must be stressed that even when inequality grounds are mentioned, they are usually considered in isolation and very few times in relation to gender or sex.

How the different inequality domains are addressed

Several initiatives have been recognised for their endeavours to suggest strategies that target the reduction of gender disparities, primarily focusing on areas such as employment, education, and care. Many of these actions primarily focus on strengthening the interconnection between women, education, and employment. Among these initiatives we can find educational programs, skill enhancement programs, and mentorship opportunities - mostly around digital or Science, Technology, Education, and Mathematics (STEM) - as remedies to tackle issues of unemployment and occupational segregation. We observed that these measures seemed to be often guided by the idea that women's problems to access the labour market, or work and labour gaps, are not embedded in structural gender+ inequalities but only due to their lack of skills and education. Many documents highlighted the primary challenges in these areas, sometimes underscoring the impact of the pandemic on these issues and emphasising the urgency of finding remedies. However, specific actions, particularly capable of instigating structural transformations, are rarely identified.

In the domain of education, we also observed that across numerous European nations, the severe phases of the pandemic led to the shutdown of educational institutions, prompting a swift transition towards diverse experiments in remote instruction. It is widely acknowledged (Engzell 2021; Haelermans et al. 2022, for instance) that these abrupt adjustments adversely affected the educational prospects of numerous students, particularly those belonging to disadvantaged demographics. Regrettably, only a few of the examined plans included provisions to tackle this specific issue.

In the domain of care, the plans address gender equity in two primary areas: enhancing working conditions within the care sector and providing support for the care of children, the elderly, and individuals with disabilities. Nevertheless, the reorganisation of care provision and the promotion of community-based care, which seems to be a positive consequence of the impact of COVID-19, pose a risk of exacerbating the gender care gap if they are not planned and implemented with a gender perspective in mind as it often observed in the plans.

In the domain of GBV, the majority of the actions mentioned in the proposals do not adequately address the specific issues that emerged during the pandemic. These measures failed to address the pressing need to enhance the resilience of support services, which were severely impacted by the crisis and faced difficulties in providing assistance to all women in need. Instead, they primarily aimed to fulfil pre-existing legal obligations, particularly those outlined in the Istanbul Convention. Consequently, the plans presented an opportunity to expedite long-overdue reforms. Moreover, the

initiatives concerning GBV predominantly focused on intimate partner violence and/or heterosexual relationships, disregarding other forms of violence and excluding LGBTIQ+ individuals, particularly youth. The absence of any mention regarding cyberviolence and strategies to combat this growing type of violence is also concerning, particularly in light of the increased digital activities resulting from the COVID-19 crisis.

In the domain of healthcare, several plans outlined broad objectives of enhancing the fairness and quality of healthcare services. Numerous plans expressed the intention to enact significant transformations in their respective national health systems, with the overarching goal of ensuring accessible services for all. However, it is worth noting that only a limited number of plans addressed gender-related inequalities, and detailed information on the mechanisms to achieve improved accessibility remains scarce. Regrettably, few tangible measures have been outlined in this regard. The measures that seem mostly to address issues connected with the pandemic are those related to investments in healthcare infrastructures, staff, and equipment. However, the lack of sufficient gender+ specific measures in addressing the COVID-19 crisis is particularly notable, considering its primary nature as a health crisis and the disproportionate impact it has had on women and other already marginalised groups.

Most of the examined plans (19 out of 26) acknowledge and tackle the domain of the gender pay and pension gap. However, it appears that in many instances, these plans merely mention a broad objective without providing specific actions to achieve it. For instance, the plans of Austria, Finland, France, Lithuania, and Luxembourg, include the goal of reducing the gender pay gap in their objectives without elaborating on the specific measures that will be taken to accomplish this goal. Instead, they indicate that existing instruments outside the scope of the plan will be utilised to address this gender-related concern. There are also various measures focusing on pension reforms, encompassing targeted adjustments to the pension supplement for childcare support, revisions to the pensionable age, and enhancements to the minimum pension amount. These reforms are usually described as having a positive impact on women and young individuals, despite being formulated using neutral language regarding gender.

In the domain of Environmental Justice, one of the conditions established by the EC for formulating the plans was the requirement to allocate a minimum of 37% of the proposed budget to initiatives that support the climate transition, green transition, and biodiversity (Bisciari et al. 2021). However, we observed that although the plans acknowledge the importance of these issues, there is a limited number of measures specifically addressing gender equality. In instances where gender dynamics are considered, the prevailing narrative emphasises how the transition in accessing and utilising energy and natural resources indirectly benefits women, who are considered the most vulnerable group at risk of exclusion from these essential resources.

Throughout the course of the pandemic, numerous cases arose where committees, predominantly led by men, were responsible for crucial decision-making processes. This situation contradicted the fundamental principle of inclusivity and equitable representation in decision-making. However, out of the 26 plans that were examined, the domain of decision-making and politics were the least prioritised area following GBV, mentioned in 42% of the plans. Upon closer examination of how this topic was approached, it becomes evident that the plans merely offered ambiguous general observations without presenting specific steps to alleviate disparities.

Inequality grounds within the plans

In the documents, we encountered numerous mentions of age, particularly concerning the education of young individuals and the well-being of the elderly. Social class was also addressed, with a focus on assisting those who are unemployed or living on low incomes. Furthermore, there were discussions regarding disability, including statements opposing discrimination and advocating for care and services. However, we observed that the plans completely neglected any consideration of disparities related to religion/belief, gender identity, and sexual orientation, which is quite striking. Although there were some references to ethnicity and nationality within the plans, they were mostly general statements against discrimination, lacking concrete measures specifically aimed at addressing inequalities based on these factors.

Civil Society and NRRPs

Most of the reactions to the plans from civil society focused mainly on criticism of the excessive weight given to policies related to the domain of the economy at the expense of measures related to social recovery. Some of these concerns regard social needs like housing, healthcare, childcare, and education, the lack of measures to fight poverty, the lack of a gender-sensitive approach (e.g., excessive focus and resources allocated to male-dominated sectors or lack of resources against GBV).

In addition, many CSOs expressed a critical viewpoint regarding their participation in the plan's drafting process. Concerns raised by these social actors encompassed inadequate engagement and inefficient methods employed for organising consultations. Additionally, CSOs voiced dissatisfaction with the lack of transparency during the design phase, highlighting instances where the plan's contents conflicted with the actual agreements in the design phase or where pertinent information regarding social dialogue was not made publicly accessible.

Conclusions

The recovery policies address topics related to the field of gender equality and often dedicate specific sections to the subject. Some plans describe the main challenges, highlighting the impact of the pandemic on these issues and emphasising the

importance of finding solutions. However, in general, it is challenging to identify specific measures, especially those that would lead to significant structural changes. This situation can be partially attributed to the framework governing the creation of the plans. Although Member States were obligated to tackle gender equality matters, the evaluation criteria did not include this theme, and there was also a lack of allocated funding. These factors might have hindered the interest of Member States in defining concrete measures. In many cases, the measures outlined aim to address other objectives, with the mitigation of inequalities for women and vulnerable groups being an indirect outcome or a result of tenuous reasoning. Furthermore, the absence of a gender impact assessment (GIA) in over half of the plans indicates a lack of commitment to finding tangible solutions for gender inequality issues.

Moreover, there is a scarcity of connections between the actions taken to address gender inequalities and the specific challenges that arose in the wake of the pandemic. For example, the limited steps taken to address GBV primarily rely on pre-existing legal obligations, such as the Istanbul Convention, rather than directly responding to the new needs and issues arising from lockdown measures.

In numerous instances, it appears that the plans were formulated primarily by assembling existing economic reforms that decision-makers had already drafted and were awaiting financial support. Since the regulations of the NRRP pushed for the consideration of gender mainstreaming during the development of these plans, many policymakers were compelled to superficially incorporate some form of "gender makeup" into reforms and investments that originally lacked a gender-sensitive approach. As a result, the outcome of this process entails numerous ambiguous and broad statements emphasising the significance of gender equality and equal opportunities. Moreover, there is a tendency (sometimes relying on creative interpretation) to retroactively identify positive indirect effects for women in measures that were not originally intended to target them.

An intersectional approach is noticeably lacking in most policies. There are mentions of various grounds such as age (particularly in relation to youth education and elderly care), social class (support for the unemployed and individuals with low income), and disability (including general statements against discrimination and provisions for care and services). However, it is important to highlight that these aspects are typically addressed in isolation, with minimal consideration given to their intersections with other identity factors, particularly gender. Notably, there is a striking absence of any discussion on inequalities related to religion/belief, gender identity, and sexual orientation. While ethnicity and nationality receive somewhat more attention in general statements against discrimination, there is a complete lack of specific measures dedicated to addressing these forms of inequality within the plans.

Finally, it is crucial for the European Commission to ensure that Monitoring and Evaluation processes place a particular emphasis on aspects of the performance system that pertain to gender equality. To mitigate the limited attention given to gender equality during the initial design of the NRRPs, one approach is to closely monitor how these measures are implemented retrospectively. Within the “performance framework”, which is an integral part of the monitoring and reporting system for this kind of expenditure, there are specific elements designed to address gender equality concerns. These include identifying national measures focused on gender equality, periodic reporting on the status of gender-disaggregated indicators, and assessing how the plans address gender-based inequalities. These measures can help rectify the issue of insufficient consideration of gender-related matters (for more information, see Linková et al. 2022).

Cycle 3 – Learning from civil society

Aims

In the first two cycles of the project, we observed that the policies designed to address the health, economic, and social impacts of the pandemic often lacked gender mainstreaming and intersectional approaches (Cibin et al. 2021; Cibin et al. 2022). The findings indicated that vulnerable groups were frequently overlooked and neglected (Axelsson et al. 2021), and they have yet to experience a proper recovery process (Sandström et al. 2022). We built upon these findings to focus the analysis of the third cycle on a deeper understanding of practices and actions that can reverse the trend of deepening inequalities. For this reason, the objective was to learn from strategies and promising practices implemented by CSOs and individuals in vulnerable situations to cope with the consequences of the pandemic. We used the concept of "better stories," developed by Dina Georgis (2013) as the foundation of the analysis. Georgis employs stories as a lens and a tool for social inquiry, combining personal and political aspects (Altınay 2019) and offering insights into the construction of political histories (Strid et al. 2022). Through this concept we did not seek to identify best practices but rather to enable the examination of actions that can serve as inspiration for public authorities and other CSOs.

From the 12th of September to the 14th of October 2022 the NR collected information about 128 civil society initiatives that supported vulnerable people during the pandemic. Among these, 31 better stories have been selected and the representatives of the CSOs involved have been interviewed. 31 interviews have been conducted following a specific grid designed by the project team. The primary objective was to comprehend the evolution of these initiatives throughout the pandemic, understand the lessons learned, explore strategies for tackling new challenges, and examine the impact of institutional factors on these dynamics. We focused on the observation of various grassroots efforts primarily initiated by formal and informal organisations within the civil society to address gender+ inequalities exacerbated by the pandemic, with particular attention to vulnerable groups.

During the pandemic, many CSOs encountered obstacles that jeopardised their operations and survival (e.g., Tago et al., 2021). At the same time, many others CSOs had a crucial role in promoting and enhancing community resilience (Isetti et al. 2022, p. 2). In numerous cases, for instance, CSOs exhibited faster responses to the crisis compared to public authorities (Pazderski et al. 2022). This has led to a widespread re- definition of the dynamics between states and CSOs (e.g., Dayson and Damm, 2020). In our study, an examination of these dynamics during the pandemic, starting from its onset until the current day, was carried out. We analysed the various adaptation processes, drew valuable insights, and made observations on the ways in which actions for change,

advocated by CSOs, interacted with both opportunities and limitations in the underlying structures. Ultimately, we were able to identify key elements that facilitated these initiatives in crafting compelling narratives, which can serve as a source of inspiration for decision-makers, other CSOs, and stakeholders seeking solutions to challenges arising from the pandemic and potential future crises.

The search for 'better stories' took place simultaneously in other WP focusing on two different aspects: the individual level (WP4) and the macro level through the analysis of quantitative data (WP3).

Key findings

Domains and inequality grounds addressed

Among the 30 initiatives selected and analysed by the NRs, the main domain considered was the safeguarding of human rights, which received attention in approximately half of the initiatives (see Figure 6).

Figure 6 The main domain addressed by each initiative is in blue and the other domains addressed are in red

These efforts encompassed various aspects, including ensuring access to social and healthcare services for vulnerable individuals, providing humanitarian aid, protecting the right of asylum-seekers, advocating for freedom of movement, securing a decent standard of living, promoting the right to adequate housing, combating poverty, establishing shelters for at-risk groups, and offering support to individuals with disabilities. Six initiatives concentrated their main domain on the realm of work and the labour market, while four initiatives centred around addressing the gender care gap and

another four aimed to tackle GBV. Two initiatives placed an emphasis on human rights in education, and one initiative had an economic focus. Notably, no initiatives were found that primarily targeted decision-making and politics, the gender pay gap, or the domain of environmental justice. However, these topics were present as secondary domains in some initiatives.

Over two-thirds of the initiatives tackle the issue of inequality related to sex and gender, and likewise, over two-thirds address concerns regarding social class and socioeconomic background (Table 2). Approximately half of the initiatives are focused on addressing age-related challenges, while one out of every three initiatives is dedicated to tackling vulnerabilities associated with disabilities.

Table 2 Number of initiatives in which there are intersections of inequality grounds

	Sex/ gender	Social class / socioeconomic background	Age	Disability	Nationality	Ethnicity	Religion/ belief	Sexual orientation	Gender identity	Other
Sex/ gender		16	10	5	6	4	0	1	3	3
Social class / socioeconomic background			10	7	9	6	0	0	1	2
Age				8	6	5	0	0	1	0
Disability					4	2	0	0	1	0
Nationality						4	0	0	1	2
Ethnicity							0	0	0	1
Religion/ belief								0	0	0
Sexual orientation									5	6
Gender identity										1
Other										

The connection between sex/gender and socioeconomic background is evident, as over half of the initiatives address these factors simultaneously. Numerous initiatives, in fact, specifically focus on women facing poverty. Table 2 also illustrates how age plays a role in conjunction with these two factors, as several initiatives observed cater to the elderly (particularly women) or the young (including women) in poverty. It is important to emphasise that in more than one-fourth of the initiatives, the intersection of nationality and socioeconomic background is highlighted, shedding light on the vulnerable situation of migrants. Additionally, a similar number of initiatives clearly demonstrate the link between age and disability, as both young and elderly individuals with disabilities required greater support during the pandemic.

The main topics and focus

While the initiatives encompass a range of topics, many of them share common concerns regarding isolation, poverty, and limited access to public services and information. One prominent theme revolves around the imperative, particularly in the early phases of the pandemic, to establish secure and hospitable shelters for individuals belonging to vulnerable groups. The interviews frequently touched upon another prominent topic, which revolves around the importance of providing minorities, particularly migrants who frequently face discrimination or isolation, with access to information, counselling, and opportunities for social interaction. Poverty is a prominent concern that is addressed by numerous initiatives, with some of them specifically dedicated to offering assistance and support to individuals facing socioeconomic difficulties (for more information see Ghidoni et al. 2023). Accessibility to healthcare services is another crucial issue.

Several initiatives were specifically developed in response to requests from women in vulnerable positions, such as those who were pregnant, victims of violence, or migrants. Examples of these initiatives concern access to services related to abortion, sexual and reproductive health or housing and support for victims of GBV. Generally, the individuals most in need of assistance belong to groups with overlapping vulnerabilities, including gender, nationality, ethnicity, and age, among others. However, a common thread among them is their low socioeconomic status.

We noticed that the pandemic and the subsequent lockdown measures not only exacerbated the challenges faced by vulnerable individuals but also complicated their recovery by abruptly altering, suspending, or shutting down various support services and sources of information. Some of these individuals were already facing difficulties, while others encountered problems due to the crisis. This situation is likely to have long-term consequences, impacting even those who are currently not considered vulnerable. For instance, the Irish interviewee described the extensive waiting lists for mental health support services as evidence of this impact.

The main tools

Our analysis showed that the CSOs in our better stories have demonstrated the capacity to navigate through crisis scenarios based on their accumulated knowledge and simultaneously cultivate adaptive capabilities. These skills have frequently emerged from increased reflexivity, fostering a deeper acknowledgment of organisational competencies. Consequently, these CSOs have been able to delegate greater autonomy to their personnel, volunteers, and beneficiaries. This collaborative commitment has resulted in the cultivation of creative and resourceful problem-solving approaches that transcend conventional boundaries.

The concept of trust is the pillar of our better stories. Trust is established between the individuals providing support and the users/recipients, with colleagues in the

organisation, with the general public and with other organisations, giving rise to a profound sense of connection. Collaboration with public authorities proved to be crucial both to enable the economic and time sustainability of the initiative and to make it more effective. Where such collaboration was not possible, greater reliance was placed on the mobilisation of volunteers and the creation of solidarity networks, through the support of existing or new alliances.

In our better stories, CSOs prioritised the well-being of individuals requiring assistance and actively strived to engage with individuals who were typically overlooked by mainstream services, often considered 'hard to reach.' To this goal, on-site fieldwork and establishing trust-based relationships with gatekeepers and beneficiaries have been described as fundamental steps to be taken. Many of these CSOs saw the digitalisation processes as an opportunity to enhance inclusivity among users and automate certain procedures to allocate more time for cultivating relationships, foster solidarity networks, and maintain consistent connections with users. Ultimately, many CSOs enhanced their fundraising capabilities.

The role of the institutional infrastructure

The initiatives were not only the result of the capability of civil society to begin or to maintain a support initiative. Conditions related to bureaucracy and the role of specific public institutions involved have emerged as pivotal factors. Among these, first and foremost, the pandemic engendered opportunities at the bureaucratic level, creating the so-called "windows of opportunity" (Kingdon 1984). These windows played a critical role in enabling CSOs to explore innovative solutions and mitigate resistance to change.

Financial support from national, regional, or local public authorities, which allocated significant resources to pandemic response, very often contributed to making these initiatives able to survive and to offer support to vulnerable people.

Furthermore, complementary state-civil society relations (Dayson and Damm 2020) took place in numerous cases, particularly when governments engaged CSOs in decision-making processes and activities of coordination pertaining to public services. Several public institutions thus validated the viability and efficacy of cooperative approaches, drawing from the expertise of those who worked directly with vulnerable populations. In times of uncertainty, diverse authorities began to acknowledge the crucial intermediary role played by CSOs.

However, the interactions between these initiatives and public authorities have not been always positive. For instance, there were instances where local institutions provided support to the CSOs while national counterparts hindered progress. In such scenarios, CSOs often relied on their experience to navigate these dynamics and seek out potential allies who were able to offer support.

Conclusions

Suggestions and recommendations have been developed for politicians and decision-makers, building on the analysis of the better stories above. First, to ensure sustainability and build resilience, CSOs require reliable and consistent funding from public authorities (for more information, see Altınay et al. 2023a). It is crucial to transition from viewing such initiatives as temporary emergency responses to establishing a permanent and stable support system for CSOs. Second, in order to tackle enduring challenges that have attracted significant attention during the pandemic, it is imperative to establish appropriate measures. The pandemic has highlighted issues require long-term solutions, such as the infringement on human rights in impoverished and marginalised circumstances, the fragile condition of public healthcare services in many nations, and the temporary halt of certain sexual healthcare services and reproductive rights within specific healthcare systems. These are just a few examples emphasising the necessity for policies to address these concerns systematically.

Third, in developing policies that affect vulnerable groups, it is crucial to engage with CSOs that directly interact with them. Their involvement can enhance the process by offering valuable insights and authentic better stories derived from their first-hand encounters. Furthermore, these policies should transcend mere reactive measures and adopt a preventive stance, emphasising collaboration across multiple sectors. Fourth, the experiences analysed confirmed how limitations on mobility, which were deemed essential to contain the transmission of the virus, exerted a significant influence on the intricate web of social connections and individuals' daily existence. It is imperative that forthcoming measures of similar nature be crafted with a greater emphasis on acknowledging the magnitude of their societal consequences, encompassing their enduring effects. In connection with the previous point, it is important to remember that public services encompass more than just a singular objective; they can be part of an interconnected network of various services. School, for instance, is not only about education; it is also about access to meals, opportunities for social interaction with peers, and the identification of domestic violence cases, among others. These additional services play a vital role in supporting vulnerable individuals. Therefore, when considering actions like suspending or terminating these services, it becomes imperative to acknowledge the associated secondary and long-term effects as well.

There is a pressing need to convert the pandemic-induced window of opportunity into a lasting scenario. Our analysis underscores the significance of providing space for civil society's expertise and innovation by reducing bureaucratic barriers and fostering a receptive attitude towards change. Consequently, the formation of coalitions comprising CSOs, and public entities has become a crucial factor in efficiently addressing intricate challenges that impact the most vulnerable segments of society.

Conclusions

The results of the analysis conducted within WP2 in the three cycles of the RESISTIRÉ project described how gender and vulnerable group inequalities emerged/increased and were managed during the various phases of the pandemic. Figure 7 schematically represents how these inequalities were taken into account by policies and civil society. In particular:

Figure 7 How different women and vulnerable people's inequalities were covered during the pandemic

1. There was an initial phase in which public policies very quickly focused mainly on containing the contagion and buffering the consequences of the various lockdown policies in the main sectors of the economy and on the support of some working categories. In such an emergency situation, these policies have contributed to making the gender inequalities present in the social fabric even more evident and they often privileged those people framed in 'traditional' or 'typical' family models, citizenship criteria, and standard employment contracts. There were some policies that tried to mitigate issues concerning women and people belonging to vulnerable groups, but they only covered small categories of people. This was despite the fact that gender mainstreaming has been

adopted as an approach in the policy making of the European institutions for two decades now and that there was a great deal of experience on how such crises mainly affect women and vulnerable groups.

2. The recovery policies, and in particular the design of common financial instruments within the European Union to mitigate the socio-economic crisis within individual states in a solidarity-based and coordinated manner, represented a fundamental opportunity to respond to the various problems that became evident in the first phase of the crisis. The resources allocated could have enabled the development not only of ad hoc solutions to individual problems, but also the attempt to deal in a structural manner with the causes of these problems, which had their roots long before the pandemic began. Moreover, these policies were no longer pressed by the need to provide instant answers to sudden problems but could already rely on early evidence and opportunities for reflection. In spite of these premises, the attention that these plans paid to gender inequality issues was often not very strong and not very interested to the signs that the pandemic brought to light. Even less attention has been paid to trying to find responses that consider the intersectional dynamics relating to different vulnerable groups.
3. In this situation, civil society has been fundamental in trying to mitigate the problems that have emerged and not been considered by policies. Where some policies, especially at the local level, have considered to support some of the most vulnerable groups, civil society has often played the role of the device through which these policies have been implemented, due to its ability to be present on the ground and create relationships of trust even in marginalised contexts. Despite this and the great experience accumulated in the field, what has often been contested by these civil society actors is their lack of involvement in policy-making processes during the pandemic, and in particular in the definition of NRRPs. In addition, the limited resources available to CSOs, the obstacles posed by the aftermath of the pandemic in being able to carry out their services in the best possible way, together with the lack of specific policies, meant that many people found it difficult to receive help during that period.

Recommendations

The findings that emerged during the three project cycles were discussed on various occasions both among the consortium members and with the involvement of experts and stakeholders. Regarding the issues noted/reported in this report, some important recommendations for policy makers were defined that will be summarised in the following section.

First, the project offered suggestions on how to mainstream gender in policies related to the pandemic and in general crisis. We underlined how in the early stages of policy

development; it is crucial to identify the primary gender-related concerns within the policy area and assess how the pandemic might affect both the policy area and its potential impacts. The GIA is an essential tool in policy design and should not be overlooked. However, it is crucial to conduct this assessment accurately and diligently, rather than using it retrospectively to find unintended benefits for women in measures that were not initially intended for them.

In the policies focusing on recovery, it is necessary to allocate dedicated funds towards measures that specifically tackle intersectional gender inequalities. This allocation should not only target traditionally male-dominated sectors such as digital and environmental fields, but also professions predominantly carried out by women like healthcare, tourism, and education. Additionally, fiscal policies need to be carefully designed to promote gender equality and contribute to both short- and long-term recovery efforts. Greater emphasis is needed on structural barriers affecting women's participation in the workforce, including obstacles related to paid work and caregiving responsibilities, unequal distribution of care duties, inadequate support for single-parent families, and parental leave policies. The focus should shift from the attempt of improving individual women towards the implementation of structural solutions.

We recommended to add gender sensitivity lens into all objectives, targets, and indicators associated with the policies; when dealing with distribution of funds for socioeconomic recovery, it is crucial to link gender mainstreaming mechanisms and criteria to specific actions, measures, and responsibilities, rather than relying on vague rhetoric and contextual information. It is also fundamental to establish mechanisms for gender-sensitive monitoring and evaluation to track progress effectively. We showed the importance of assigning specific responsibilities to dedicated actors, to ensure accountability throughout the process. It is also crucial for all actors involved in the policy process to receive adequate gender training. Seeking external gender expertise and involving target groups directly in the decision-making process can also contribute to a more inclusive and effective policy. Lastly, increasing the participation of diverse women and vulnerable groups in policy making is key to addressing gender+-related concerns comprehensively.

Collaboration with CSOs and individuals working directly with communities and vulnerable groups is essential in areas like research, reporting and generating media coverage to shed light on the experiences of marginalised groups. CSOs also offer excellent examples of the importance of adopting intersectional strategies when tackling crisis-related concerns. Representatives of CSOs should be involved both in the policy making process and in the monitoring and evaluation processes. For this reason, it is crucial for authorities to establish accessible communication channels to reach out to the CSOs and ensure they understand the information provided about new policies and their consequences. Additionally, authorities should offer support to CSOs, as they often play a significant role in communicating such information to vulnerable people.

Furthermore, we stressed the importance of organising workshops and meetings that bring together representatives of diverse communities, sectors, and issues, to analyse the effects of policies. We underlined the importance of utilising gender+ disaggregated data whenever possible, often produced by CSOs.

The experience of the pandemic offered further proof of how in order to ensure effective communication during crisis, it is crucial that both men and women have equal participation in scientific and political discourse within the media. Women should not be limited to minor and stereotypical roles when it comes to conveying information. It is essential to broaden the scope of communication channels to cater to diverse segments of the population, ensuring that everyone has access to accurate and comprehensive information about the emergency.

The sudden digital acceleration during the pandemic on the one hand helped to keep people connected but on the other hand increased issues of digital divide or new inequalities. For this reason, it is necessary that this transition takes place with the most vulnerable people in mind, both by working on digital accessibility but also by providing offline channels that allow for true inclusion. As the experiences of many CSOs have shown, a hybrid transition seems the most appropriate solution to avoid excluding anyone.

Finally, we propose a new approach to understanding crises by viewing them as a continuum (for more information, see Altinay et al. 2023b). This perspective emphasises how various sites of crisis (such as homes, workplaces, schools, hospitals, public spaces, etc.) and different phases of crises (prior to, during, and after) are interconnected. While the most conspicuous manifestations of a catastrophic event may be confined to a specific time or place, their repercussions transcend these boundaries. Additionally, when adopting a gender-inclusive and intersectional viewpoint, we recognise that our world is characterised by a web of interrelated crises encompassing GBV, poverty, racism, state violence, climate change, and other protracted forms of harm and calamity.

Further research

The analysis carried out within WP2 also produced some reflections on the need to conduct further research on specific areas. Here we provide an overview of some of the main topics encountered and we encourage to read the project's research agendas to obtain more detailed information.

Our analysis revealed that men predominantly held decision-making positions in many countries, although some exceptions showed a higher representation of women. The evaluations conducted by NRs provided mixed evidence regarding the correlation between the gender composition of decision-makers and the gender sensitivity of

policies. No clear pattern emerged to determine whether decision-maker composition influenced the presence or absence of gender-sensitive policies. This presents an interesting topic that requires further analysis. Furthermore, it would be interesting to examine whether an increased presence of women in governments has affected the composition of their scientific and technical committees.

The lack of attention given to vulnerable groups such as migrants, women in shelters, and sex workers raises concerns about the deliberate use of "strategic ignorance" by public authorities. This concept refers to "the mobilisation of the unknowns in a situation in order to command resources, deny liability in the aftermath of disaster, and to assert expert control in the face of both foreseeable and unpredictable outcomes" (McGoey 2012, p. 555). Further investigation is needed to determine if public authorities intentionally utilised ignorance to prevent, confuse, or divert emerging knowledge about inequalities and vulnerable populations.

The pandemic represented a window of opportunity that allowed civil society to experiment and to innovate. This exceptional situation needs to be transformed into a permanent condition. This can be achieved by reducing administrative barriers that hinder the possibility to adapt to different changing situations. In order to effectively address intricate challenges faced by the most marginalised, it has also become imperative to establish alliances between CSOs and public entities. These coalitions play a vital role in managing complex issues impacting vulnerable populations. We think that further study would be necessary to understand what kind of coalitions between CSOs and institutions should be formed to allow these processes to take place.

We observed that many CSOs considered the digital transition as a way to enhance work processes and internal information sharing within organisations, also enabling service providers to stay connected with various initiatives and fellow users, fostering resilient networks. At the same time, it is necessary to better study: if in this processes CSOs have considered strategies to also involve those without digital devices literacy and/or skills; what kind of hybrid (online and face-2-face) formats of activities with the users the CSOs have developed after the end of the lockdowns; the disadvantages brought by the digital transition process in the relationship between CSOs and users.

As also noted above, RESISTIRÉ's innovative approach based on design thinking and a step-by-step methodology allowed to put together the triangulation of different research methods with the co-design activities of specific outputs (recommendations, pilot projects, research agenda, etc.). This approach made it possible to collect, analyse and share a large amount of data in a very short period of time. This proved to be crucial in trying to provide immediate answers to the questions raised by the pandemic within national contexts that were in many cases very different.

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